

USING THE SCIENTIFIC HERITAGE OF MEDIEVAL SCHOLARS IN MATHEMATICS LESSONS

Masharipova Gulsara

General secondary school No. 32, Yangiariq district,
Khorezm region Mathematics teacher

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7560294>

Abstract: This article highlights the scientific heritage of Central Asian figures who contributed to the science of mathematics. Recommendations on using the scientific heritage of Middle Eastern scholars in mathematics lessons are also presented.

Keywords: Mathematics, Education Act, Scholars, Education System, Indian Accounts.

The adoption of the Law on Education, the transition to a two-level system of training highly qualified specialists, requires that the knowledge provided to students be more consistent and as comprehensive as possible. The purpose of teaching mathematics in the educational system is to familiarize students with the mathematical apparatus necessary for solving theoretical and practical problems, to develop logical thinking and to raise the general level of mathematical culture, to create the ability to mathematically examine problems encountered in practice. Modern sciences are divided into three parts (social, natural and technical sciences) depending on their content. Each of these forms a whole system, covering many related disciplines. Mathematics is an important field in the system of sciences and means "Science" in Greek. Also, mathematics is one of the ancient sciences, and it formed and improved other sciences such as arithmetic, geometry, later algebra, mathematical analysis, and analytical geometry. Below we will study the activities of scientists who made discoveries in mathematics.

The thinkers of the Ancient East, especially the countries of Central Asia, made a great contribution to the development of mathematics, we will touch on some of them:

Al-Khorazmi. (783-850) Muhammad ibn Musa Al-Khorazmi was born in Khorezm and studied at a religious school and a madrasa. He founded "Bayt Al-Hikmat" ("House of the Wise") in Baghdad, gathered leading scientists of his time and led them. Khorezmi in his treatise "Indian Calculation" describes the system of numbers consisting of 0,1...,9 for the first time in Arabic, and this system was transferred from him to Europe. He was the first to distinguish linear and quadratic equations in his work "Al-Jabr walmuqabala" and described

the method of solving them. Algebra is derived from the Latin word Al-Jabr. Al-Khorazmi was the first author of zij-mathematical and astronomical tables.

Abu Raykhon Beruni. (973-1048). Abu Raykhan Beruni Muhammad ibn Ahmed is a great medieval scholar. He writes in his work "Geodesia" that he determined the geographical width of the city of Qiyat. Beruni writes in "History of India" that the meridian of the globe is 110,895 km. This is smaller than the current calculation (111.1 km), i.e. it was only 205 m wrong. His work "Kanuni Masudi" is devoted to astronomy, in which he writes about his discoveries related to trigonometry and spherical trigonometry. He is the author of 22 works on mathematics, 10 works on astronomy, 38 works on mineralogy, physics, etc.

Mirzo Ulugbek (1394-1449). Muhammad Taragay-Ulugbek, son of Shahrukh Mirza and grandson of Amir Temur, is a great scientist and statesman. Ulugbek's main work is called "Zizhi Ko'ragoniy", it contains the calculation of the year, a trigonometric table with an accuracy of up to four digits, in which the values of sine and cosine that differ by one minute are given. Trigonometric tables are calculated with an accuracy of 10 decimal places, and the values of sine and cosine in these tables are compiled with an interval of one minute. Zijda Ulug'bek wrote a separate treatise on calculating the sine of one degree. Equator deviation related to astronomy, determining the coordinates of skylights, determining the geographic latitude of an arbitrary point on the earth, and determining the distance between stars and planets are described. Ulugbek calculated the calendar of lunar and solar eclipses and the list of 1018 stars and their location, given the latitude and longitude relative to the equinox point in 1437. He was executed by the enemies of science at the age of 55.

Ahmad Farghani. (died in Baghdad in 861) Abul Abbas ibn Muhammad ibn Kasr Farghani was a great astronomer, mathematician and geographer. Fergani, Al-Khorazmi and other scientists worked in Baghdad and conducted research in "Bayt Al-Hikmat". In his work entitled "Introduction to Astronomy", he described the work of previous astronomers, corrected their shortcomings, and predicted the solar eclipse of 812. Farghani's book "On the Collection of Celestial Movements and the Science of Astronomy" is the first book on astronomy in the Arabic language. It describes the making and use of astronomical instruments, one of the most necessary instruments, the groom's clock. Ferghani described the properties of the sphere and its sections in different positions in his work "About Making Asturlab".

Omar Khayyam. (1048-1123). Ghiyasiddin Abdulfath Umar ibn Ibrahim AlKhayyam was born in Noshipur and studied in Bukhara and Samarkand. Omar

Khayyam in his book "Treatise on the Proofs of Al-Jabr and Al-Muqabalah" expanded the concept of number to a real positive number, that is, he introduced the concepts of square and cube and described some cubic equations and methods of solving them. Omar Khayyam in the book "Comments on the difficulties in the introduction to the book of Euclid" states the famous postulate V of Euclid as a theorem, develops it and makes a great contribution to the development of geometry. In the calendar proposed by him in his work entitled "Zizhi Malik Shoshi", 8 out of 33 years are leap years, the duration of the year is $365 \frac{8}{33}$ days, the error of this calendar is 19 seconds per year.¹

Ibn Sina (*Avitsena*) (980-1037). Abu Ali ibn Sina was born in the village of Laglaqa, Vobkent district, Bukhara region. At the age of ten, Ibn Sina studied algebra, geometry and even philosophy, he knew the names of all the constellations and could clearly point them out. Ibn Sina described his great experience in medicine and his incomparable knowledge in philosophy, algebra, astronomy, chemistry and other fields of science in "The Book of Healing", "The Laws of Medicine", "The Book of Knowledge". Ibn Sina's works total more than 280. In the arithmetic section of his "Book of Healing" he explains natural numbers and their properties. Ibn Sina uses operations on natural numbers to check, that is, he compares the numbers according to their modulo nine.

References:

1. Joraev T.J. etc. Basics of higher mathematics. Part 1. Tashkent "Uzbekistan" 1995. 280 pages
2. Soatov Yo.U. Higher mathematics. Part 1. Tashkent. 1992. 496 pages.
3. Latipov H. et al. Analytic geometry and linear algebra. Tashkent. "Uzbekistan" 1995.
4. Kharatova, S. K., & Ismailov, T. X. O. G. L. (2022). Use of innovative technologies in the educational process. *Science and Education*, 3(3), 713-718.

¹ Kharatova, S. K., & Ismailov, T. X. O. G. L. (2022). Use of innovative technologies in the educational process. *Science and Education*, 3(3), 713-718.

